

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MAWA****FIRST NAME: RATIB****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes) 401d

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-QUIZ (PERIODS ONE TO FIVE)

1. **What is the aim of writing an academic essay?**
 - To persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.¹**
 - To facilitate inter-academician learning.
 - To store knowledge generated by scholars for future use.
 - To enable Ph.D. students to learn how to write proper academic papers.
2. **What is the difference between conceptual and practical research questions?**

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd Ed, (Bangui: EUCLID University, 2019), 1-4.

- For conceptual questions, the answer to the “so what?” helps readers to understand an issue but for practical questions, it tells readers what to do to solve a problem or an issue.²**
 - For conceptual questions, the answer to the “so what?” tells readers how to solve an issue but for practical questions, it helps readers to understand an issue.
 - For practical questions, the answer to the “so what?” does not tell readers what to do to solve the problem but conceptual questions seek to solve a practical problem.
 - Conceptual questions seek to understand an issue but practical questions seek to solve a practical problem by first researching to understand the problem.
3. **Why is it important to evaluate sources of literature for relevance and reliability when conducting a research study?**
- To eliminate irrelevant sources of information and improve the reader's confidence in the results of the study.³**
 - To identify the right sources of information needed to build the background information and support evidence generated during the conduct of the study.
 - To help Ph.D. students gain the skills and knowledge required for identifying plausible sources of information to cite for their dissertation projects.
 - To recognize the authors of best-written research evidence that will help inform the next course of research in a specific field.

² Turabian, Kate L, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations*, Eighth Ed., Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Wayne C. Booth (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15-17

³ Ibid., 28.

4. **What is the importance of building a research project storyboard when implementing your Ph.D. dissertation project?**

Helps in planning for evidence search, organize research arguments, prepare draft dissertation reports, and test the final copy of the dissertation.⁴

Storyboards are only necessary when conducting a small research project.

Storyboards help Ph.D. dissertation supervisors to track the progress of students.

Storyboards are important for identifying the right research topic, research questions, and hypothesis for Ph.D. research projects.

5. **Which of the following set of reasons explain why researchers need to cite sources of information used during research conduct?**

To give credit to authors, assure readers of accuracy of facts, show readers research tradition that informed your work, and help readers extend or follow your research.⁵

To justify research conduct, promote good research conduct practices, help students plan their research work, and credit the authors.

Recognize the authors, grade quality of research conducted by universities, provide background information for the dissertation.

Provide confidence to readers, evaluate the importance of sources of information, provide justification for the research, and create a reference list for the dissertation.

6. **Which of the following statements describes the notes-bibliography style of citation?**

⁴ Ibid, 22.

⁵ Ibid, 86.

- Use of sources of information signaled by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which a researcher refers to the source.⁶**
 - The name of the authors and page numbers are placed at the end of the sentence in which the researcher refers to the source.
 - The number not superscripted is placed at the end of the sentence to signal the source of information cited.
 - Either a superscript number or author's names and page numbers are placed at the end of the sentence in which the researcher refers to the source.
7. **Why is important to accurately use punctuations in academic writings?**
- Punctuations show pauses and emphasis on certain ideas in research text hence helps strengthen arguments in academic writing.⁷**
 - Punctuations show accurate use of both American and British English Language relevant for academic writing.
 - Punctuations improve reader's confidence and make reading an academic text enjoyable.
 - Punctuations may be relevant for academic writing and only those recommended by the Students University or faculty should be followed when writing a thesis or a Ph.D. dissertation.
8. **What is the recommendation from the WHO style guide (in-house rule) on the use of numbers in technical and research publications?**

⁶ Ibid., 90.

⁷ Ibid., 173-180.

- Spell out whole numbers less than 10 and use figures for those above 10, figures should always be used together with symbols or abbreviations, numbers should be spelled out if used at the beginning of a sentence, use figures for numbers in series, numbers with more than four digits should be split using non-breaking space.⁸**
 - Spell out whole numbers more than 10 and use figures for those below 10, figures should always be used without symbols or abbreviations, numbers should be spelled out if used at the beginning of a sentence, use figures for numbers in series, numbers with more than four digits should be split using non-breaking space
 - Spell out all numbers, figures should always be used together with symbols or abbreviations, numbers should not be spelled out if used at the beginning of a sentence, use figures for numbers in series, numbers with more than four digits should not be split using non-breaking space
 - Spell out whole numbers less than 100 and use figures for those above 100, figures should always be used together with symbols or abbreviations, numbers should not be spelled out if used at the beginning of a sentence, use figures for numbers in series, numbers with more than four digits should be split using non-breaking space
9. **What set of factors should Ph.D. students consider when identifying and developing a researchable topic?**
- The potential audience, intellectual value and worth of the study, personal and professional goals, and issues of ethical consideration.⁹**
 - Curiosity, the interest of the Ph.D. student, a practical problem affecting society or community, and professional goals.

⁸ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 17-18.

⁹ Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008), 5-7.

- Intellectual value and worth of the study, availability of resources, the usefulness of the results, and curiosity of students.
- Ethical considerations, the curiosity of the student, availability of resources, and potential audiences.

10. **What is the difference in evaluation criteria used for qualitative and quantitative research studies/papers?**

- Quantitative studies use validity and reliability standards to identify a good and convincing study, while qualitative studies are evaluated using credibility and dependability criteria to determine their trustworthiness.¹⁰**
- Both qualitative and quantitative studies employ the same criteria of Validity and reliability to determine the worth of a study.
- Qualitative researchers do not evaluate studies to determine their trustworthiness; however, quantitative researchers determine the worth of their studies using validity and reliability criteria.
- The differences between the two research approaches lie only in their methodology. Qualitative research generates numbers and qualitative studies generate text data only.

¹⁰ Ibid., 76-78.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.